

PRIMARY PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDIES OF *CATUNAREGAM SPINOSA* (THUNB.) TIRVEN FOR SECONDARY METABOLITES

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ABSTRACT

Catunaregam spinosa (Thunb.) (Rubiaceae), commonly called as Gedhphal and madanaphala in Ayurveda. Various ethno medicinal aspects are present in folk literature and new scientific documentation. It has been reported that *Catunaregam spinosa* used in diarrhoea, dysentery and as abortifacient, anthelmintic and antipyretic. Phytochemical extraction was carried out for qualitative test for secondary metabolites presence in different part of *C. spinosa*. Plant was collected, parts are dried and fine powder was subjected to different solvent extraction with soxhlet apparatus. The result for test showed presence of Alkaloids, Cardiac glycosides, Coumarins, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols, Reducing sugars, Saponins, Steroids, and Tannin in Leaves extract, Stem Bark extract and Root bark extract which varies according to variation in solvent system. Results reveals that the importance medicinal properties is due to the presence of these phyto-constituents which need to farther elaboration in future works to detect active ingredient for particular disease.

KEY WORDS: Phytochemical, Secondary metabolites, *Catunaregam spinosa*, Solvents.

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INTRODUCTION

Catunaregam spinosa (Thunb.) Belongs to the family Rubiaceae commonly known as Gedhpal or Emetic nut. Though the traditional Indian system of medicine has a long history of use, they lacked adequate scientific documentation, particularly in light modern scientific knowledge.^{1,2} It consists of about 10 species, out of which two are in India with medicinal important mentioned in Ayurveda. Plant bark reported for the treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery and as abortifacient, anthelmintic and antipyretic.³ It is also considered to be sedative and hypoglycemic and also used in case of stomach ache as first aid remedy, roots are used in the treatment of epilepsy, eye ache and urinary infection, fruit is used as fish poison, emetic and the leaves are used in Pulmonary Infections.^{4,5} It is carminative, alexiteric, antipyretic; cures abscess, ulcers, inflammations, wounds, tumours, skin diseases.⁶ It contains triterpenoidal saponins, essential oil, veleric acid, tannins and resin.^{7,8} The present study is designed to explore the preliminary phytochemical and physicochemical analysis of *C spinosa* leaf, which is responsible for its pharmacological properties. The various analyses carried out for both the plants *C. spinosa* and *P. zeylanica* have shown varied and

appreciable results. *Catunaregam spinosa* and *Pavonia zeylanica* were used in our study to evaluate the preliminary physicochemical and phytochemical analysis.⁴ The current study deals to find out the possible ingredient of plant responsible for its medicinal properties. The present investigations were carried out to for qualitative estimation of secondary metabolites among different part of the plant with respect to different solvent system.^{9,10} Phytochemical investigations of crude plant extracts and herbal plant extract shows the presence of active principles in the plant parts like bark, leaves, flowers, roots, fruits, seeds etc.^{21,23} The effect and activity of plant secondary metabolites are always playing a important role in the plant medicine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

Catunaregam spinosa plant was collected from the forests of Toranmal of Shahda (21.840213° N, 74.456583° E) of Nandurbar Distract (Fig.1). Taxonomical identification was completed with the help different flora like Flora of Presidency of Bombay, Flora of Dhule and Nandurbar District and recorded taxonomical characters.^{11,3}

Figure 1
Catunaregam
Spinosa (Thunb)

Figure 2 A =Extraction by Soxhlet
B = Extraction in different Solvent
C = Phytochemical Test

Laboratory work

Different part of the plant viz. Leaves, Stem bark and Root bark were shad dried and grinded into thin powder for extraction procedures and phytochemical test. Extractions are carried to each powdered plant material (Leaves, Stem bark and Root bark) to successive solvent extraction by Soxhlet methods. Six different solvents systems viz. water, methanol, ethanol, chloroform, petroleum Ether and acetone were used to study phytochemical profile.^{21, 23} Proportion of material to solvent was taken as 1:10 (w/v). Material soaked for 72 hrs. In umber color bottles and filtered with

Whatmann filter paper 1. Extract obtain from different material were subjected to following phytochemical analysis (Figure 1.)

Phytochemical Test

As per the available literature, different tests were designed for estimation of secondary metabolites as Alkaloids, Anthraquinone, Cardiac glycosides, Coumarins, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols, Reducing sugars, Saponins, Steroids, Tannin and Triterpenes. For each test standred procedure and observations has been made in replicates for validation of result (Table.1).

Table1
Procedures and observation for Phytochemical test with relative references

Sr. No	Test	Procedure	Observation	References
1	Alkaloids	0.5 ml extract + treated with few drops of 1ml 2N HCl +Mayer's reagent / Dragandorf reagent and Hager's reagent	Orange precipitate, Orange color, White or Yellow ppt.	12
2	Anthraquinone	Few drops of extract was boiled with 10% HCl for few minutes and cool + CHCl ₃ (Chloroform)to filtrate and few drops of NH ₃ added and heated	Rose pink color obtain	13
3	Cardiac glycosides	0.5ml extract + 1ml water + aqueous solution NaoH some drops for coloration appearance	Brown or violet ring below and greenish ring at lowest part	14, 12
4	Coumarins	2 ml of extract added with 3 ml of 10% NaOH	Appearance of yellow color	15
5	Flavonoids	0.5ml extract + 5-10 drops of dilute Hcl + small amount / pieces + then boiled for few min. Shinodaw's Test , Zn-HCl acid reduction Test	Red or appearance of Magenta color	15, 16, 12
6	Glycosides	Anthrone + H ₂ SO ₄ + Heat	Purple or green	15, 13
7	Phenols	FeCl ₃ Sample + lead acetate + water	Intense color Formation of white ppt	15 14, 13
8	Reducing sugars	0.5ml extract was dissolved in 5ml of water and filter it + boiled with Fehling's solution A & B for few min.	Orange red precipitate positively detects reducing sugars.	17, 13
9	Saponins	Sample + water + shaking	Formation of honey comb like froth	15, 14, 13
10	Steroids	Salkowski's test and Liebermann burchard's test	Dark green color in the upper layer and red color in the lower layer	18, 15, 13
11	Tannin	0.5ml of aqueous extract + 10% lead acetate few drops	Greenish-black colouration	18, 12, 13
12	Triterpenes	Liebermann Test Salkowski Test Noller's test	Bluish green , Red & fluorescent, Pink color OR Reddish-brown coloration	14, 6, 14, 13

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The followings are the results from the phytochemical of *Catunaregam spinosa* for Leaves, Stem bark and Root bark in six different solvent extracts. Soxhlet extract result for Aqueous (Aq), Methanol (M), Ethanol (E), Pet-Ether (Et), Chloroform (C) and Acetone (A) (Table 2.). Leaves, stem bark and root bark powder of *C. spinosa* shows positive result from extraction in Aqueous, Methanol and Ethanol extract for various phytochemical among all tested. Same is not always true for chloroform and acetone extract among all tested phytochemical with the help of soxhlet extraction methods as mention in table 2. Phytochemical properties as resulted in table

2. predicts the active components responsible for abortive activity²⁰, diarrhoea and dysentery⁷ like activity found in stem and fruit and sometime in root bark of the plant. Plant also important in rheumatism, relieve pain of bruises and bone aches during fevers and to disperse abscesses^{9,19}. For leaves, Stem Bark and Root Bark sample it was found that all phytochemical are present except Anthraquinone and Coumarins among all parameters in six different solvent.²¹ By considering these literature aspects we tried to reveals the facts regarding the chemical ingredients in different plant parts.^{22,23}

Table 2
Results for Phytochemical test of *Catunaregam spinosa*

Sr. No.	Phyto- constituents	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i>																	
		LEAVES						STEM BARK						ROOT BARK					
Solvent System	Aq	M	E	Et	C	A	Aq	M	E	Et	C	A	Aq	M	E	Et	C	A	
1	Alkaloids	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
2	Anthraquinone	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	Cardiac glycosides	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-
4	Coumarins	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	Flavonoids	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
6	Glycosides	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
7	Phenols	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
8	Reducing sugars	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
9	Saponins	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
10	Steroids	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+
11	Tannin	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-
12	Triterpenes	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-

“+” indicates presence of phytochemical and “-” indicates absence of phytochemical

CONCLUSIONS

The current work for *Catunaregam spinosa* found that there is very significance medicinal important of plant

among tribes. The present investigation shows positive result for Alkaloids, Cardiac glycosides, Coumarins, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols, Reducing sugars, Saponins, Steroids, Tannin and Triterpenes in all different solvents. As mention in above result table 2

there is a variation in the presence and absence of some phyto-constituents with respect to plant part as well as change in solvents. Variations due to solvent changes are due to polar and non polar property of solvent.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Conflict of interest declared none.

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